

EUCALYPTUS GLOBULUS FINGER JOINTED SOLID TIMBER AND GLUED LAMINATED TIMBER WITH SUPERIOR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES: CHARACTERISATION AND APPLICATION IN MULTILAYER STRAINED GRIDSHELLS

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Abstract

This work establishes the main guidelines to produce high-performance *Eucalyptus globulus* Labill finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber laths and analyse their potential for application in multilayer strained gridshells. To this end, a proposal for strength grading of eucalyptus solid timber is firstly provided, combining visual and mechanical criteria. The bending strength of industrially produced eucalyptus finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber laths using different wood grades and two adhesives (1C-PUR and MUF) is investigated. The results suggest that strength classes D55 for finger jointed solid timber and GL56 for glued laminated timber, or even higher, could be reached by appropriately graded solid timber and adhesive. Moreover, the superior performance of eucalyptus products over those made of other species in terms of the minimum design radius of curvature, considering rheological aspects, and the stiffness of multilayer curved systems with semi-rigid connections as shown by FEM analysis, is discussed. Finally, eucalyptus products are successfully used in two full-scale strained gridshells, highlighting the promising future for this species here.

Keywords

Eucalyptus globulus, bending characterisation, strength grading, finger jointed solid timber, glued laminated timber, gridshell, active bending, radius of curvature, multilayer system, structural analysis.

1. Introduction

Gridshells are highly efficient and light structures for roofing medium to long spans. Recent advances and the popularization of form-finding tools, BIM, structural optimization and CNC manufacturing have allowed architects and engineers to explore the design potential of this type of structures [1].

Increasing demands for sustainability and developments in engineered wood products are making impressive timber gridshells possible. Different techniques can be used [2], from straight glued laminated timber elements and complex steel joints as in the Exeter gridshell [3] or the Pods Sports Academy [4], to curved and warped glued laminated timber members, as in the Centre Pompidou-Metz or the Nine Bridges Country Club [5]. Both techniques require singular element manufacturing, with the corresponding impact on construction costs.

However, there is another possible procedure for gridshell construction. This is based on the elastic bending of identical very long small cross-section timber laths to achieve the desired shape, assembled using conventional connection systems. This technique was proposed and intensively investigated by Prof. F. Otto and other colleagues after 1960. Structures using this technique were originally called *gridshells* [6], and they are now known as *elastic gridshells* [7], *bending active gridshells* [8] or *strained gridshells* [9] to differentiate them from the other timber gridshells whose members are not elastically curved, as is the case with the Exeter or Pompidou-Metz gridshells.

From an economic point of view, the structural concept of strained gridshells is very appealing [10] due to its high potential for standardization, its not requiring curved laminates, the use of very little wood and no need for costly metal joints. However, despite their potential this type of structure has not been widely used. Only a few major examples such as the Mannheim Multihalle (1975) (Fig. 1 left) [11], the Weald and Downland Open Air Museum (2002) (Fig. 1 middle) [12] or the Savill Garden gridshell (2006) (Fig. 1 right) [13] with 60, 15 and 25 meters of maximum span, respectively, have been built since the first works of Prof. Otto. This has been due mainly to different scientific-technological barriers [14], such as the complexity of form-finding methods to determine the structural geometry generated by the elastic deformation of its members and the lack of suitable

1 timber products that are easily available on the market. While research into strained gridshell form-finding are
2 increasingly numerous [15-19], there are nearly no studies on the development or characterization of timber
3 products [20]. This has led some researchers to work with other materials such as glass fibre reinforced polymers
4 [21,22].

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12 **Figure 1.** The Multihalle gridshell (left), Weald and Downland gridshell (middle) and the Savill Garden gridshell (right).

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14 One of the first and most important decisions in a strained timber gridshell project is therefore appropriate
15 selection of the wood species to be used, according to two basic criteria: 1) the possibility of obtaining very long
16 economic products such as finger jointed solid timber, in order to avoid the use of numerous and unsightly
17 mechanical joints; and 2) the possibility of obtaining high-quality wood (as defect-free as possible) to avoid
18 premature failures during the bending process.

19
20 Western hemlock was used in the Mannheim Multihalle gridshell because of its very straight grain, so that long
21 finger-jointed laths could be obtained, reducing the number of connections. Green oak was chosen for the Weald
22 and Downland gridshell due to its good bending capacity and lower cost than dry oak. Although oak has major
23 grain deviation, joining short (60 cm average length) pieces by finger-joints minimised this problem. Larch was
24 used in the Savill Garden gridshell because of its high quality and local availability. The elastic deformation
25 process requires lath cross-sections to be small. $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$, $50 \times 35 \text{ mm}^2$ and $80 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ of finger jointed solid
26 timber were used in the Mannheim, Downland and Savill gridshells, respectively. To obtain quality wood and
27 avoid failures during bending, careful wood selection and extensive experimental campaigns to guarantee finger-
28 joint strength were performed for the said three gridshells. Although this is obviously possible in singular works,
29 to increase the use of strained gridshells, it would be desirable to have suitable commercial products which do
30 not require experimental tests for each project.

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32 Moreover, species with good mechanical properties, mainly in terms of high bending strength and modulus of
33 elasticity, would be very appropriate for strained gridshell construction since smaller radii of curvature could be
34 used. They would also substantially improve structural anti-buckling behaviour, which is usually one of the
35 critical aspects in the design of this type of structure [7]. Thus using wood from species with superior properties,
36 such as hardwoods, is of great interest.

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38 Currently there are not commercial finger jointed solid timber using hardwood in Europe. However, in the last
39 15 years there has been a proliferation of glued laminated products of different hardwood species such as meranti
40 [23], chestnut [24], oak [25,26] and beech [27]. Many of them have better mechanical properties than softwood
41 laminated products [28], attaining 5th percentile bending strength up to 48 N/mm^2 (GL48c) in the case of beech
42 [27]. Nevertheless, none of these products are less than 76 mm thick (as they have to be manufactured with a
43 minimum of 3 or 4 lamellae), so their use in strained gridshells is really limited.

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45 A hardwood of great interest is *Eucalyptus globulus* L. It is a temperate-climate species which grows in southern
46 Europe, Australia and South America. In Europe it is one of the three structurally characterized timber species
47 with the best mechanical performance, along with beech and ash. Although it is usually used as a raw material
48 for pulp and paper, in recent years there has been increasing industrial and institutional interest in using it to
49 develop higher added-value building and engineering products [29-35].

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51 Previous studies by Golfín *et al.* (1997) [36] of Spanish *Eucalyptus globulus* L. reported mean values of bending
52 strength, modulus of elasticity and density of 91.97 MPa, 18.43 GPa and 797 kg/m^3 , respectively, highlighting
53 the good performance of this species. These studies provided the visual grading criteria adopted by Spanish
54 standard UNE 56546:2013 [37] as well as the data needed for its inclusion in European standard EN 1912:2012
55 [38]. According to this, Spanish *Eucalyptus globulus* L. has a single visual grade, MEF, and it is assigned to D40
56 strength class (according to EN 338:2018 [39]), the same as German beech and ash of LS13 grade (according to
57 DIN 4074-5:2008 [40]). *Eucalyptus globulus* L. also usually presents few small knots due to a natural pruning
58 process. This feature, together with its high mechanical properties, make it a timber species of great interest for
59 use in structures where high-performance materials are required, such as strained gridshells. Despite the potential
60 of the species, it is currently not used in any certified commercial structural product.

To obtain high-performance timber products, raw material strength grading and developing a high strength finger-joint are key steps.

Regarding strength grading, research carried out on European beech shows that combined use of visual and mechanical grading criteria is necessary to classify high mechanical performance lamellae [41,42]. Different studies conducted to date have shown that the modulus of elasticity of hardwoods such as beech, ash or oak provides good correlations for strength prediction, while density is not an appropriate parameter for this purpose [43,44]. To date, no similar studies for *Eucalyptus globulus* L. grading using combined criteria (visual and mechanical) have been performed.

Only one recent work developed by the authors [31] can be found in literature on the development of a high-performance finger-joint in *Eucalyptus globulus* L. This study analysed the influence of different factors on the finger-joint strength of specimens assembled in the laboratory using single-component polyurethane (1C-PUR). Each specimen was made up of twins from the same board to control of the material properties and independently analyse their influence on finger-joint strength. It was pointed out that a high-performance finger-joint was possible with proper finger geometry and pressure indicating GL48 strength class or even higher. However, an experimental campaign with a random distribution of industrially produced twins would be required for definitive conclusions.

The European product standards for the manufacture of finger jointed solid timber, EN 15497:2014 [45], and glued laminated timber, EN 14080:2013 [46], are only valid for softwoods and poplar. To date there are no European standards for the manufacture of finger jointed solid timber or glued laminated timber made of hardwoods.

This work studies the development of high-performance products with a characteristic bending strength higher than 40 MPa made of *Eucalyptus globulus* L. More specifically, small cross-section finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber for use in strained gridshells are investigated. Firstly, a proposal for the strength grading of solid eucalyptus timber is reported, discussing the influence of density and modulus of elasticity. This is of interest for gridshells and for the development of high-performance laminated timber products. Secondly, the characteristic bending strength values of industrially produced finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber are shown, analysing the influence of the proposed strength grading and different adhesives (1C-PUR and MUF). The advantages of the superior mechanical properties of eucalyptus products over other species regarding fundamental aspects in the design of multilayer strained gridshell are then discussed. Finally, two full-scale strained gridshells made of eucalyptus designed by the authors are presented.

2. Characterisation of eucalyptus laths

2.1. Materials and methods

2.1.1. Raw material

Eucalyptus globulus Labill. from the northern Galicia region in Spain was used in this study. 300 boards of 2-3 m in length cut from heartwood (with no juvenile wood) with radial annual ring orientation were prepared. This orientation minimises the strong tendency of this species to deform due to high shrinkage anisotropy and other specific growth characteristics during drying [47].

All of the boards were visually graded according to Spanish standard UNE 56546:2013 [37], which guarantee at least D40 strength class. The most important requirements established by this standard are: 1) maximum knot diameters of 1/3 the width or 1/2 the thickness; 2) 10% maximum slope of grain; and 3) the depth of drying fissures at the board end shall not exceed board width. Approximately 10% of the boards were rejected.

Before testing, the boards were conditioned at 20°C and 65% relative humidity until equilibrium moisture content (MC) was reached. 183 boards were used for solid timber tests. The remaining boards were used for finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber tests.

2.1.2. Solid timber

Edgewise bending tests under four-point loading according to EN 408:2012 [48] was performed on the one hundred eighty-three 32 mm thick, 95 mm wide and 2090 mm long eucalyptus boards, to obtain the bending strength (f_m) and the static modulus of elasticity ($E_{m,0}$). The test span was set at 18 times the depth (width of

cross-section). The tension edge was selected at random. All tests were conducted under displacement control. Load and deflection were recorded during testing.

MC was determined by the oven-dry method in accordance with EN 13183-1:2002 [49] using a section taken from each board. It resulted in a mean value of 11.2%. The material density (ρ) was also measured using a section taken from each board according to EN 408:2012 [48], giving a mean value of 843 kg/m³ (CoV=12%). The moduli of elasticity and density values obtained were adjusted to the reference moisture content of 12% according to the procedure outlined in EN 384:2018 [50].

Characteristic values were estimated by determining the fifth percentile according to EN 14358:2016 [51] using parametric methods. Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) tests were used to examine probability distributions. Normal distribution fitted the bending strength variable better than lognormal distribution. Modulus of elasticity and density data were analysed while assuming normal distribution.

For bending strength, the reference dimensions correspond to 150 mm height (h) as stated in EN 384:2018 [50]. As the specimens' height was 95 mm, a size adjustment to 150 mm was made by dividing the fifth percentile by the k_h factor expressed in Eq. (1) [50].

$$k_h = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(\frac{150}{h} \right)^{0.2} \\ 1.3 \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

2.1.3. Finger jointed solid timber

Three batches of industrially produced finger-jointed solid timber were prepared with the aim of analyzing the influence of the timber quality and the type of adhesive. Before batches preparation, edgewise bending tests under four-point loading according to EN 408:2012 [48] were performed on the boards to determine the elasticity moduli.

The first batch was formed of randomly selected boards covering the entire range of elasticity moduli (equal or greater than 10000 MPa). Twelve laths 95×32 mm² in cross-section and 9 m long were manufactured. A distance between finger-joints of 55 cm was chosen as the reference to minimize fibre deviation defects, similarly to the Downland gridshell [12]. A single-component polyurethane (1C-PUR) adhesive type I, LOCTITE® HB S309 PURBOND, was used to glue the finger-joints. After the gluing process, the laths were planed to a final cross-section of 89×30 mm² and cut into pieces of around 55 cm in length with a finger-joint located approximately in the middle of the length, giving a total of 185 specimens.

In order to obtain higher strength values than in batch 1, a second batch was prepared by subtracting the boards with a modulus of elasticity of less than 15000 MPa. Two laths of finger jointed solid wood were manufactured with the same dimensions and adhesive as in batch 1, resulting in 24 specimens.

Finally, in order to study the influence on strength of a different adhesive, a third batch analogous to the second one (timber pieces from the same boards in both batches, with a modulus of elasticity higher than 15000 MPa) but using Melamine Urea Formaldehyde (MUF) instead of 1C-PUR were prepared. MUF system GripPro™ Design, which consists of GripPro™ Design Adhesive A002 and GripPro™ Design Hardener H002 was chosen. This too gave a total of 24 specimens.

All of the finger-joints were manufactured with tangential orientation, with the finger geometry configuration and end pressure that provided the best results in previous research carried out by the authors [31].

Four-point bending tests according to EN 408:2012 [48] with a $15h$ span (being h the depth) were performed in order to determine finger-joint strength. Since the elastic bending of the laths around the weak axis of inertia is usually more important in strained gridshells, especially if the laths follow geodesic paths, it was decided to perform the bending tests flatwise (depth=thickness). All of the tests were conducted under displacement control.

Characteristic bending strength data processing was assessed according to the procedure specified in EN 14358:2016 [51], applying the parametric method with a normal distribution assumption derived from K-S goodness-of-fit tests.

2.1.4. Glued laminated timber

Since numerous finger-joint failures during construction have been documented in the most important timber strained gridshells built to date [11-13], it was decided to develop glued laminated timber laths composed of two thin layers. In addition, the laminate makes it possible to improve possible defects such as local grain deviations or cross-section distortions due to the lack of radial orientation.

Six finger-jointed lamellae of eucalyptus were therefore manufactured industrially with the same requirements as those set for batch 1 ($E_{m,0} > 10000$ MPa and 1C-PUR adhesive) but with a cross-section of 85×20 mm² and 7 m in length. The finger-jointed lamellae were planed afterwards to a final cross-section of 80×18 mm². Three glued laminated laths were produced by flat bonding two lamellae using 1C-PUR adhesive combined with a primer pre-treatment following the procedure described in [30]. Finally, the glued laminated laths were planed to a final cross-section of 75×30 mm² and cut into pieces of around 60 cm long, obtaining 35 specimens. All of the specimens had a finger-joint in the central third of their length.

The glued laminated laths were characterised by performing four-point flatwise bending tests according to EN 408:2012 [48] with an 18h span. All specimens were tested by placing the finger-joint on the tension face. The tests were conducted under displacement control.

2.2. Results and discussion

2.2.1. Strength grading of solid timber

Mean values for bending strength $f_{m,mean} = 91.4$ MPa, modulus of elasticity $E_{m,0,mean} = 18108$ MPa and density $\rho_{mean} = 843$ kg/m³ were obtained, which confirm the great potential of *Eucalyptus globulus* L. The comparison of f_m , $E_{m,0}$ and ρ values in the present work with previous studies [36] indicates that the investigated population covers the full spectrum.

The correlations of bending strength with density (Fig. 2) and with static modulus of elasticity (Fig. 3) for all the tested boards are presented.

Figure 2. Correlation between bending strength and density.

Figure 3. Correlation between bending strength and static modulus of elasticity.

As can be seen, density has no influence on bending strength and therefore should not be considered as an indicator in the grading process. On the contrary, modulus of elasticity shows a marked correlation and is an appropriate physical indicator to optimize the grading process. Similar conclusions have been reported for other hardwood species such as beech, ash or oak [43,44,52].

Reaching greater strength classes by increasing visual grading demands is always a possibility. This was studied in [36], which concluded that a D50 strength class was not possible even by decreasing the maximum knot diameter (to less than 1/6 the width and less than 1/4 the thickness) and grain deviation (to less than 7%). In fact, the resulting values barely improved on those obtained by considering the entire population. The reason was that approximately 75% of the analyzed boards had very small knots or none. The boards used in the present work had similar characteristics and therefore the possibility of a different visual grading was not considered.

According to the previous results and considerations, and with the aim of obtaining boards of high strength classes (higher than the D40 class assigned in EN 1912:2012 [38]), three grading proposals with 1, 2 and 3 different grades were made, based on the static modulus of elasticity of the boards.

The mean values of density (ρ_{mean}), static modulus of elasticity ($E_{\text{m},0,\text{mean}}$) and bending strength ($f_{\text{m},\text{mean}}$) together with the corresponding standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CoV) obtained for the different grading proposals are shown in Table 1. The number of boards (n) corresponding to each grade as well as the percentage with respect to the total (%) are also shown.

Table 1 Mean values, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CoV) for bending strength, modulus of elasticity and density of eucalyptus boards grouped by grades.

		Proposal 1		Proposal 2		Proposal 3		
		P1-1	P2-1	P2-2	P3-1	P3-2	P3-3	
$E_{\text{m},0}$ (MPa)		≥ 10000 (all)	≥ 10000 to 15000	> 15000	≥ 10000 to 15000	> 15000 to 20000	> 20000	
n		183	38	145	38	85	60	
%		100	21	79	21	46	33	
f_{m} (MPa)	mean	91.4	71.0	96.8	71.0	91.5	104.3	
	SD	21.6	15.4	19.7	15.4	19.4	17.8	
	CoV	24%	22%	20%	22%	21%	17%	
$E_{\text{m},0}$ (MPa)	mean	18108	13183	19399	13183	17783	21688	
	SD	3415	1277	2499	1277	1303	1932	
	CoV	19%	10%	13%	10%	7%	9%	
ρ (kg/m ³)	mean	843	758	866	758	858	877	
	SD	102	86	93	86	100	82	
	CoV	12%	11%	11%	11%	12%	9%	

Characteristic bending strength ($f_{\text{m},k}$), mean modulus of elasticity ($E_{\text{m},0,\text{mean}}$) and characteristic density (ρ_k) for all grades, and a tentative of strength class assignment according to the criteria set out in EN 338:2018 [39], where $f_{\text{m},k}$, $E_{\text{m},0,\text{mean}}$ and ρ_k must match or exceed the class values, are included in table 2.

Table 2 Characteristic bending strength, mean modulus of elasticity and characteristic density of eucalyptus boards grouped by grades, and tentative strength class assignment according to EN 338:2018.

	Proposal 1		Proposal 2		Proposal 3		
	P1-1	P2-1	P2-2	P3-1	P3-2	P3-3	
$E_{\text{m},0}$ (MPa)	≥ 10000 (all)	≥ 10000 to 15000	> 15000	≥ 10000 to 15000	> 15000 to 20000	> 20000	
$f_{\text{m},k}$ (MPa) ($h=95$ mm)	53.1	42.6	61.7	42.6	56.7	72.2	
$f_{\text{m},k}$ (MPa) ($h=150$ mm)	48.3	38.8	56.1	38.8	51.6	65.6	
$E_{\text{m},0,\text{mean}}$ (MPa)	18108	13183	19399	13183	17783	21688	
ρ_k (kg/m ³)	663	600	700	600	678	729	
Tentative strength class assignment	D45	D35	D55	D35	D50	D60	

The first proposal serves as a reference and includes a single grade (P1-1) for all the tested boards ($E_{\text{m},0} > 10000$ MPa), so it coincides with the visual grading. The values of $f_{\text{m},k} = 48.3$ MPa, $E_{\text{m},0,\text{mean}} = 18108$ MPa y $\rho_k = 663$ kg/m³ are similar to those obtained in [36] and reported in UNE 56546:2013 [37] ($f_{\text{m},k} = 47$ MPa, $E_{\text{m},0,\text{mean}} = 18430$ MPa y $\rho_k = 672$ kg/m³), which shows that it is not possible to reach D50 strength class with the visual grading criteria of that standard. It should be noted that *Eucalyptus globulus* L. was assigned to D40 strength class according to the old version of EN 338 [53] which did not include the D45 strength class. Further studies could lead to new assignment of this species to D45.

The second proposal includes two grades (P2-1 and P2-2), setting an $E_{\text{m},0}$ limit of 15000 MPa between them. This proposal makes it possible to assign 80% of the boards to a strength class higher than D45, specifically D55 (P2-2). In return, the remaining 20% of the boards (P2-1) would be assigned to D35 strength class.

Finally, the third proposal subdivides P2-2 grade into two grades (P3-2 and P3-3) with the aim of reaching the highest possible strength class for a large number of boards (around one third). The P3-3 grade achieved by boards of $E_{m,0} > 20000$ MPa meets this requirement and reaches D60 strength class.

The results show that mechanical grading methods in addition to standard visual grading criteria make it possible to considerably increase the assignment of strength classes to the boards, in a similar way to what happens for other hardwoods [41, 43].

2.2.2. Bending strength characterisation of finger jointed solid timber

The mean, SD and CoV values of bending strength for the three tested batches of finger jointed solid timber are outlined in Table 3. It also includes the corresponding timber grades according to the proposals presented in the previous section.

Table 3 Flatwise bending strength of finger jointed solid timber with PUR and MUF adhesives.

		Batch 1	Batch 2	Batch 3
		PUR	PUR	MUF
		P1-1	P2-2	P2-2
		$E_{m,0} \geq 10000$	$E_{m,0} \geq 15000$	$E_{m,0} \geq 15000$
n		185	24	24
$f_{m,j,flat}$ (MPa)	mean	83.5	91.6	98.1
	SD	11.0	11.8	9.7
	CoV	13%	13%	10%

As can be seen, the mean strength values of batches 1 and 2 made using PUR adhesive do not reach the mean values of the corresponding timber grades (see Table 1). However, batch 3 made with MUF yields slightly higher values. In any case, it should be taken into account that mean bending strength values of solid timber refer to 95 mm depth specimens so that, due to size effects, greater timber strength values would be expected for a 30 mm depth (corresponding to finger jointed solid timber tests). In fact, the predominant failure mode during testing was produced along the bondline of the finger-joint profile rather than in the wood in the three batches.

Table 4 displays the characteristic values of flatwise bending strength $f_{m,j,flat,k}$ (from tests) and edgewise bending strength $f_{m,j,edge,k}$ (estimated as explained below), as well as a tentative strength class assignment for finger jointed solid timber produced from laths of different grades with a strength class higher than D40.

European standard EN 15497:2014 [45] for finger jointed solid timber establishes the k_f factor to convert flatwise bending strength, $f_{m,j,flat}$, into edgewise bending strength, $f_{m,j,edge}$, according to the following expression (Eq. 2):

$$f_{m,j,edge} = f_{m,j,flat} / k_f \quad (2)$$

where k_f should take the value of 1.25 when the finger-joints are visible on the face perpendicular to load direction, as is the case. However, a broad study reported in [54] showed that $k_f=1.25$ may be insufficient for small cross-sections. Taking into account the data provided by this study, $k_f=1.38$ has been considered in the present work.

Table 4 Bending strength profiles of finger jointed solid timber according to timber grading proposals.

Proposal-Grade	Tentative strength class assignment for solid timber	Adhesive	Bending strength profile			
			$f_{m,k}$ (MPa) ($h=95$ mm)	$f_{m,j,flat,k}$ (MPa)	$f_{m,j,edge,k}$ (MPa)	Short name
P1-1	D45	PUR	53.1	63.9	46.3	Euca 45 P1
P2-2	D55	PUR	61.7	69.4	50.3	Euca 50 P2
		MUF		79.8	57.8	Euca 55 P2
P3-2	D50	PUR	56.7	66.6	48.3	Euca 45 P3
		MUF		78.7	57.0	Euca 55 P3

According to the aforesaid standard for finger jointed solid timber (which is only valid for softwood), the characteristic bending strength of the finger-joints must be greater than the characteristic values of the solid timber. With this condition, finger jointed solid timber can be directly assigned to the strength class of the solid timber from which it comes. As can be seen in Table 4, this condition is only met by P1-1 grade, and by P2-2 and P3-2 grades when MUF adhesive is applied. However, for P2-2 and P3-2 grades finger jointed using PUR, the characteristic finger-joint bending strength are lower than that of the timber, and therefore the assignment of

a strength class is limited by finger-joint strength. P3-3 grade corresponds to laths of $E_{0,m} > 20000$ MPa. Although no tests have been carried out on laths of this grade, it can be considered on the safe side that the characteristic finger-joint bending strength will be at least that corresponding to laths of $E_{0,m} > 15000$ MPa (P2-2 grade). Under this consideration and using MUF adhesive, at least D55 strength class would be reached for P3-3 grade. Further research into this grade is necessary to determine whether strength classes higher than D55 are possible.

2.2.3. Bending strength characterisation of glued laminated timber

Table 5 shows the mean values, SD, CoV and characteristic bending strength of the tested glued laminated timber specimens composed of two thin lamellae.

Table 5 Bending strength of glued laminated timber produced with P1-1 grade solid timber.

		P1-1
		$E_{m,0} \geq 10000$ MPa
n		35
$f_{m,g}$ (MPa)	mean	61.3
	SD	8.8
	CoV	14%
$f_{m,g,k}$ (MPa)		45.2

As can be seen, the characteristic bending strength of glued laminated timber manufactured with P1-1 grade lamellae (exclusively visual grading) is 45 MPa, corresponding to the characteristic bending strength of the strength class assigned to that grade (D45).

The bending strength values of the finger-joints ($f_{m,j,flat,k}$) discussed in the previous section make it possible to assume that even higher $f_{m,g,k}$ values can be achieved for other grades such as P2-2 and P3-2 (visual and mechanical grading), since these grades provide higher characteristic values for timber strength, $f_{m,k}$ (Table 2), and finger-joint strength, $f_{m,j,flat,k}$ (Table 4).

Fig. 4 shows $f_{m,g,k}$ and $f_{m,j,k}$ values for different strength classes of homogeneous glued laminated softwood [46], of combined glued laminated chestnut, oak and beech wood [24, 25, 27], and of glued laminated eucalyptus produced with P1-1 grade lamellae referred as Euca GL45. Likewise, the $f_{m,j,flat,k}$ values obtained for the different grades and adhesives (see section 3.2) are also included in the figure.

Figure 4. Characteristic timber and finger-joint strength values for different glued laminated products.

It can be seen in this figure that the characteristic timber and finger-joint strength values obtained for Euca GL45 are similar to those of beech GL44c. Taking beech glulam values as the reference, for finger-jointed eucalyptus manufactured with P3-2 and P2-2 grades of solid timber using PUR, strength classes GL46 and GL48 could be attained, respectively. These two grades show far higher finger-joint strengths when they are assembled using

MUF. With this adhesive, really high strength classes such as GL56 or even higher could be attained. A similar improvement in finger-joint strength when using MUF instead of PUR was reported in beech [55].

3. Application in multilayer strained gridshells

The mechanical properties obtained when using *Eucalyptus globulus* L. laths show better performance than softwoods and other hardwoods.

For a better understanding of eucalyptus products' potential for application in strained gridshells, it is necessary to compare their mechanical properties (f_m , $E_{m,0}$ and ρ) with those of other species in terms of two fundamental aspects in the design of this type of structures: minimum curvature design radius and stiffness in multilayer structural systems.

3.1. Minimum design radius in elastically curved laths

When designing strained gridshells, engineers have to carefully control the stresses produced by the curving process. This is fundamental, since breaks during construction can occur. Inadmissible stresses may also occur during the service life of the structure, due to a combination of residual stress and stress produced by live loads. In order to verify the bending capacity of *Eucalyptus globulus* L., several preliminary compression tests under displacement control were conducted on thin 3 m long eucalyptus laths to cause lateral bending (controlled buckling). These tests showed that large deformations were possible before failure (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. *Eucalyptus* lath subjected to compression test.

Some studies on active bending structures have analysed the curving capacity of different building materials, focusing on FRP and GFRP materials [21,56]. Nevertheless, very few studies have focused on analysing curvature radii in wood products. Research into the minimum characteristic radius of curvature of various wood-based products and different strength classes can be found in [20]. However, none of these works analyze the minimum design radii of different wood species while considering actual mechanical properties rather than strength class values, the material's safety factor and rheological behaviour.

In a rectangular cross-section lath curved around one of its inertia axes, maximum initial bending stress, σ_0 , is produced at the end fibres farthest away from the said axis. This stress value is directly proportional to the longitudinal modulus of elasticity in bending, $E_{m,0}$, and lath thickness, b , and it is inversely proportional to the radius of curvature, R , according to Eq. (3):

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{E_{m,0}}{R} \frac{b}{2} \quad (3)$$

As is known, the bending stress value falls over time due to the stress relaxation phenomenon in wood subjected to constant deformation [57]. The bending stress for a time t may be obtained from the initial stress, σ_0 , following Eq. (4):

$$\sigma_t = f(t) \frac{E_{m,0}}{R} \frac{b}{2} \quad (4)$$

where $f(t)$ is a time-dependent function that is 1 for $t=0$, and decreases in value as t increases until reaching a stationary value at infinite term. At any time t , the minimum design radius is reached for a stress equal to the design strength of the material $f_{m,d}$. Eq. (4) can then be rewritten in the form:

$$R_{\min,t,d} = f(t) \frac{E_{m,0}}{f_{m,d}} \frac{b}{2} \quad (5)$$

Following EN 1995-1-1:2016 [58], the design strength $f_{m,d}$ is obtained as $f_{m,d} = f_{m,k} / \gamma_M$. Accordingly, Eq (5) can be expressed as follows:

$$R_{\min,t,d} = \frac{f(t)}{k_{\text{mod}}} \frac{E_{m,0}}{f_{m,k}} \frac{b}{2} \gamma_M \quad (6)$$

where $f_{m,k}$ denotes the characteristic bending strength of the product; k_{mod} is a normalized strength modification factor that takes service class and load duration effects into account; and γ_M is the partial material factor.

It can be seen that minimum design radius is a function of the ratio between the stress relaxation function and the strength modification factor (rheological parameters), the ratio between the modulus of elasticity and the characteristic strength of the material (mechanical parameters), lath thickness (geometrical parameter) and the safety factor.

The $f(t)/k_{\text{mod}}$ ratio in Eq. (6) provides information on the relative evolution between the strength reduction (k_{mod}) and the fall in bending stress ($f(t)$) throughout the entire life of the structure. This aspect is essential to determine the most unfavourable scenario (short or long term).

Regarding the values to be considered for $f(t)$, unfortunately current standards do not include information on this, since it is not a usual engineering problem. However, according to previous research carried out by the authors [57], Eq. (7) could be assumed as a conservative approximation on the safe side in service class 1:

$$f(t) = \frac{1}{1 + k_{\text{def},t}} \quad (7)$$

where $k_{\text{def},t}$ is a normalized creep function value which appears in current standards such as EN 1995-1-1:2016 [58]. For service class 1, $k_{\text{def},0}=0$ and $k_{\text{def},\infty}=0.6$. Therefore, $f(0)=1$ and $f(\infty)\approx 0.6$ can be taken.

Regarding the k_{mod} values to be considered, it is necessary to make an important first observation. While EN 1995-1-1:2016 provides k_{mod} values for elements subjected to constant load (e.g. beams under permanent load) to avoid creep failure caused by increases in deformation, k_{mod} values for structures subject to constant deformation (e.g. strained gridshells) are not included in the standard or the scientific literature. If it is assumed that the reduction in strength produced under constant strain (stress relaxation) is similar to that produced under constant load (creep), then the values provided by the standards could be used. However, authors such as Aondio *et al.* [59] state that $k_{\text{mod}}=1$ for service class 1 and any load duration could be assumed in structures where creep failure is prevented by appropriate form and boundary conditions. Obviously, the determination of k_{mod} is a key aspect in sizing elastically curved timber laths.

For service class 1, if values of $k_{\text{mod}}=1$ for $t=0$ and $k_{\text{mod}}=0.6$ for $t=\infty$ are assumed according to EN 1995-1-1:2016 for elements subjected to constant load, then the $f(t)/k_{\text{mod}}$ ratio takes a value of approximately 1 for any time t . This hypothesis makes it possible to disregard aspects related to rheology when only bending stresses due to curving act. If, on the contrary, a value of $k_{\text{mod}}=1$ is considered for any duration of the load as stated by Aondio *et al.* [59], then the $f(t)/k_{\text{mod}}$ ratio is greater in the first instants of structural life. In the present work, $k_{\text{mod}}=1$ for all load durations and service class 1 is assumed. For service classes 2 and 3, if the corresponding k_{mod} and k_{def} values from EN 1995-1-1:2016 are assumed, and we continue considering that $f(t)=1/(1+k_{\text{def},t})$, it can be observed that the $f(t)/k_{\text{mod}}$ ratio is also higher in the first moments of structural life. These facts show that stress relaxation occurs faster and with greater magnitude than strength loss and, therefore, the most unfavourable load scenarios are produced in the short or medium term.

The $E_{m,0}\gamma_M/f_{m,k}$ ratio in Eq. (6) is a very useful way of comparing, with a single glance, the bending capacity of different species and products. It is very important to realize that the $E_{m,0}$ values stated in the EN 338:2018 standard for every strength class cannot be used in the analysis of bending stresses due to the curving process. These values do not correspond to any specific species and are reference values which guarantee that any species assigned to a specific strength class (according to EN 1912:2012) will at least match the $E_{m,0}$ value of the strength class in question. Although this is obviously very useful and conservative for the determination of deformations, it can dangerously underestimate bending stresses. This is because the modulus of elasticity of a species can be significantly higher than that of the strength class to which the species is assigned. This issue can be easily confirmed in *Eucalyptus globulus* L., which exhibits an $E_{m,0}$ value of around 18 GPa, while the strength class to which it is assigned (D40) establishes only 13 GPa, which would provide initial stresses 40% lower than the actual ones. This fact makes it necessary to disregard the strength class concept in initial stresses analysis and, on the contrary, to work with strength profiles using actual species $E_{m,0}$ values.

Fig. 6 shows a comparison of the curving capacity of finger jointed solid timber (referred as “species+ $f_{m,k}$ ”) and glued laminated timber (referred as “species+GL+ $f_{m,k}$ ”) made of different species, based on $E_{m,0}$ and $f_{m,k}/\gamma_M$ values. According to the considerations pointed out before, $E_{m,0}$ and $f_{m,k}$ values have been taken from specific literature or ETAs, not from the strength class. The eucalyptus designations correspond to those defined in the previous section. According to EN 1995-1-1:2016, $\gamma_M=1.3$ for finger jointed solid timber and $\gamma_M=1.25$ for glued laminated timber are assumed.

Figure 6. Curving capacity comparison of finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber, produced with softwoods (in brown), hardwoods (in blue) and eucalyptus (in black).

The $E_{m,0}\gamma_M/f_{m,k}$ ratio corresponds to the tangent of the line which joins a specific species point with the coordinate's origin. Broadly speaking, it can be stated this ratio ranges from 375 to 800. Obviously, the smaller this value, the smaller the radius of curvature that can be achieved. A value of 540 can be established as a virtual limit which divides species (and products) into two large groups according to their bending capacity: a first group composed of all softwoods and some medium strength hardwoods such as oak and chestnut; and a second group composed of high-performance hardwoods such as eucalyptus and beech. Some glued laminated hardwoods (Chestnut GL30, Oak GL32 and Beech GL32) and high quality softwoods (Larch 30 or Pine 35) are located close to the virtual limit line.

Ratios below 515 are obtained for all eucalyptus qualities, which highlights the great bending capacity of this species. The best eucalyptus quality (Euca 55 P3) shows a ratio below 420, which implies that dry eucalyptus has an even greater bending capacity than green oak wood (used in the Downland gridshell [12]). In addition, this value is very close to the minimum ratio of all the examined products, which corresponds to glued laminated beech GL48. However, eucalyptus shows substantially higher $E_{m,0}$ and $f_{m,k}$, indicating an interesting advantage in the sizing stage of the structure.

Minimum design radii can be calculated using Eq. (6), taking as $E_{m,0}$ and $f_{m,k}/\gamma_M$ those values presented in Fig. 6. The minimum instantaneous design radii ($R_{min,0,d}$) for 30 mm lath thickness products with different species in service class 1, considering the load case of internal bending forces acting alone, is shown in Fig. 7. Hardwood laminated products are not included, given that their minimum manufacturing thickness is 76 mm.

Figure 7. Minimum instantaneous curvature design radii for 30 mm lath thickness.

As can be seen in the figure, eucalyptus makes it possible to achieve curvature radii significantly smaller than is the case with other species. In other words, for a given radius R , lower utilization ratio U (Eq. 8) and higher stress reserve σ (Eq. 9) than with other species can be obtained.

$$U = \frac{f(t)\sigma_0\gamma_m}{k_{mod}f_{m,k}} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma = k_{mod} \frac{f_{m,d}}{\gamma_m} - f(t)\sigma_0 \quad (9)$$

Fig. 8 plots curves R vs. U (in blue) and R vs. σ (in brown) for service class 1, $t=0$ and several species, considering 30 mm lath thickness.

A: Euca 55 P3; B: Euca 55 P2; C: Euca GL45; D: Euca 50 P2; E: Larch 30; F: Pine 35; G: Oak 30; H: Chestnut 27; I: Spruce 28; J: Spruce 18; K: Pine 20

Figure 8. Utilization ratio and stress reserve for different curvature radii.

Obviously, the minimum design radii yield $U=1$ and null stress reserve. For any other radius, it can be observed that eucalyptus laths show a lower utilization ratio and, in particular, a stress reserve superior to the other species. This is because eucalyptus has a very low $E_{m,0}/f_{m,k}$ ratio and a very high $f_{m,k}$. For instance, for a theoretical radius of 12 m, U values between 0.50 and 0.63 are obtained with eucalyptus depending on its quality, while Oak 30 or Spruce 18 score 0.73 and 0.92, respectively. Regarding the stress reserve σ , values from 13.5 to 20 MPa are obtained with eucalyptus, while oak or spruce barely reach 6.2 and 1.2 MPa, respectively. This important difference in stress reserve means that with *Eucalyptus globulus* L., structures can be designed that would be impossible with other species. For other instants of time, U and σ values increase with decreasing $f(t)$.

Of course, it is desirable to reduce bending stresses due to the curving process to a minimum, in order to have the greatest possible structural reserve. To this end, one solution would be to reduce lath thickness, although this entails a reduction in stiffness. This contradiction is inherent to strained gridshells, and in most cases it leads to using multilayer systems.

3.2. Stiffness of multilayer curved systems

As was shown in the previous section, maximum lath thickness in strained gridshells is limited by the design radii. This means that when lath cross-section is insufficient to resist bending out of plane, increasing lath depth may not be possible. In such cases, multilayer composite systems emerge as a very effective solution.

The multilayer system in strained gridshells is created by mechanically connecting the laths after the curving process. The design radius of the individual laths is thereby maintained while a composite section with significantly greater stiffness than the individual laths is achieved. The connection system between the different timber layers is based on the use of mechanical fasteners that produce semi-rigid joints. This connection can be made in different ways: at the nodes using bolts, as in the Mannheim Multihalle [11] (Fig. 9 left); at the members by means of timber shear blocks fixed with screws to the laths, as in the Savill gridshell [13] (Fig. 9 middle); or at both places, as in the Downland gridshell [12] (Fig. 9 right), in which shear blocks at the members and a steel patented connection at the nodes were used.

Figure 9. Multilayer connection systems: Mannheim Multihalle gridshell (left); Savill Garden gridshell (middle); and Weald and Downland gridshell (right).

The bending stiffness out of plane in a timber gridshell depends on several parameters, such as its geometric configuration and boundary conditions, the elastic properties of the wood species (E_{mean} and G_{mean}) and the stiffness and position of the multilayer connections.

The stiffness of one connection for each shear plane, $K_{\text{shearplane}}$, can be determined by Eq. 10:

$$K_{\text{shearplane}} = n \cdot K \quad (10)$$

where n is the number of connection elements and K is the slip modulus of each connection element. EN 1995-1-1:2016 [58] provides expressions to determine the slip modulus of different connection elements in serviceability limit state (SLS), K_{ser} . For dowel type elements such as bolts or screws, Eq. 11 can be applied:

$$K_{\text{ser}} = \frac{d}{23} \rho_{\text{mean}}^{1.5} \quad (11)$$

where K_{ser} is expressed in N/mm, d is the connection element diameter (in mm) and ρ_{mean} is the mean density of the timber species (in kg/m³). The slip modulus at ultimate limit state (ULS), K_u , can be calculated as $(2/3)K_{\text{ser}}$

[58]. Fig. 10 illustrates K_{ser} value variation with respect to timber density for different diameters of connection elements.

Figure 10. Relationship between K_{ser} and timber density for different diameters of connection elements.

As can be seen in this figure, for a given connection element diameter, increasing the density entails significant gains in the slip modulus of the connection elements. In particular, eucalyptus ($\rho_{mean}=843 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for P1-1 grade) presents very high slip moduli values, at 21.6% greater than oak and up to 171.6% higher than that of spruce.

Although some works explore the influence of different geometric factors (shape, size, boundaries, grid, etc.) on the stiffness and stability of strained arches and strained gridshells [7, 66-68], to the best knowledge of the authors no studies cover the influence of species. Here, a first approximation to the influence of timber species properties (E_{mean} , G_{mean} y ρ_{mean}) on the stiffness of multilayer curved systems is performed by means of the numerical analysis of a multilayer arch.

Finger jointed solid timber of different species were studied. Namely, eucalyptus (used in a full-scale laboratory gridshell prototype, see subsection 3.3) and oak and larch (species used in some of the most relevant strained gridshells) were chosen. These species were completed with spruce and pine in order to have a wide range of values for E_{mean} , G_{mean} and ρ_{mean} . E_{mean} values were taken from the referenced literature. Accordingly, G_{mean} and ρ_{mean} were derived from the following relationships: $G_{mean}=E_{mean}/16$ and $\rho_{mean}=1.2 \rho_k$ (ρ_k also from the referenced research). The mechanical properties assigned to each species are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Mechanical properties assigned to each species.

	E_{mean} (N/mm ²)	G_{mean} (N/mm ²)	ρ_{mean} (kg/m ³)
Euca P1-1	18108	1132	843
Pine 35 [61]	15103	944	604
Oak 30 [65]	13500	844	740
Larch 30 [63]	12100	756	575
Spruce 18 [60]	10700	669	433

A circular arch geometry of 15 m span, 1 m sagitta and cross-section formed of two $75 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$ laths 60 mm apart was chosen (Fig 11). These dimensions correspond approximately to one of the arches of the Pemade gridshell (a permanent gridshell designed by the authors, see subsection 3.3). To better understand the influence of the number of connections, distances between the shear blocks axes of approximately 0.5 m and 1 m were studied, these being common spacings between connection elements in the most important gridshells [11-13].

Figure 11: Arch geometry.

The numerical model was developed using RFEM (Dlubal Software GmbH). The timber laths were modeled as bar elements to which the actual cross-section and elastic properties of the studied species were assigned (Table 6). The shear blocks were also modelled as $75 \times 225 \text{ mm}^2$ cross-section bar elements. Previous analysis by the

authors proved that the longitudinal modulus of elasticity assigned to the shear blocks had no impact on the results, because their bending deformation was negligible. For this reason, it was decided to assign the shear blocks the same elastic properties as the rest of the bars, despite the fact that their fibres are rotated 90° with respect to the axis of the bar. Linear and elastic material behaviour was assumed.

A spring was placed at each end of the shear blocks to simulate the semi-rigid behaviour of the connection. These springs were assigned the stiffness corresponding to a shear plane, $K_{\text{shearplane}}$. The shear blocks were connected to the laths by means of small infinitely rigid bars which made it possible for the slip plane to be located at the actual position. Figure 12 shows a detail of the multilayer system considered (left), the deformation due to shear stress (middle), and a scheme of the implemented numerical model (right).

Figure 12. Multilayer system connection: detail (left); deformation due to shear stress (middle); implemented numerical model (right).

Two external loads were considered in the analysis of the arch: a dead load, g , corresponding to the structural weight; and a live load, q , corresponding to snow (0.15 kN/m) applied on one half of the arch to cause bending. The stresses due to elastic curving of the laths were introduced as strain loads, c . This approach made it possible to input residual stresses without modelling the actual assembly process.

Since the described arch is very slender (in the same way as gridshells), it has noticeably non-linear behaviour. It was therefore considered advisable to analyze deformations at different load levels. For this, non-linear geometric large deformation analysis was performed in which g and c were applied in a first load step, while q was introduced incrementally. Incremental analysis allows us to know the load factor by which q must be multiplied to achieve a certain deformation level or to produce global instability of the arch.

For low deformations, corresponding to SLS, mean values of the material elastic properties ($E_{\text{mean,d}}$ and $G_{\text{mean,d}}$) and the slip modulus (K_{ser}) were used. In this analysis, only the instantaneous action of the loads and not the deferred effects were considered. The load combination $g+q+c$ was studied for this purpose.

For very large deformations close to global instability situations, the design values of the material elastic properties ($E_{\text{mean,d}}$ and $G_{\text{mean,d}}$) and of the slip modulus of the joints ($K_{\text{u,d}}$) were used as stated in EN 1995-1-1:2016 [57]. They were obtained respectively by dividing E_{mean} , G_{mean} and K_{u} by the partial material factor γ_{M} , the latter taking the value of 1.3 corresponding to finger jointed solid timber. The load combination $1.35g+1.5q+0.66c$ was considered for this situation (0.66 corresponds to stress relaxation at six months [57]). Since this is nonlinear instability analysis, a geometric imperfection was applied. This imperfection was generated from the deformation corresponding to the first elastic buckling mode in the first order. The imperfection amplitude was set at 20 mm.

Figs. 13 and 14 show the load factor versus displacement curves for SLS and ULS, respectively, of the five species studied, with shear blocks at 0.5 m intervals and connected by two 6 mm diameter screws in each shear plane. Likewise, the curves of eucalyptus wood for 1 m distance between shear blocks are plotted.

Figure 13. Relationship between load factor and displacement in SLS for different species, with 0.5 m and 1.0 m distances between shear blocks (s).

Figure 14. Relationship between load factor and displacement in ULS for different species, with 0.5 m and 1.0 m distances between shear blocks (s).

Eucalyptus globulus performs far better than the other species analyzed. To reach a displacement of 50.6 mm ($L/300$), eucalyptus requires 31.2% more load than oak, 52.9% respecting larch and 84.1% with respect to spruce (see Fig. 13). Fig. 15 shows a representative deformed shape of the arch when 50.6 mm of maximum displacement (u) is reached. The increase in percentages required to reach the load that produces instability are very similar: 29.5% in the case of oak, 51.4% in larch and 83.9% in spruce. The superior performance of eucalyptus makes it possible to achieve stiffer arches with half the number of shear blocks (corresponding to a 1 m separation) than in the case with larch at 0.5 m spacing between shear blocks, and similar stiffness to oak or pine with 0.5 m spacing. This is very interesting both from an executional and aesthetic point of view, since it makes it possible to design arches with fewer connections and a lightweight appearance.

Figure 15. Representative arch deformation (amplification factor=10) for a maximum nodal displacement of 50.6 mm.

In order to analyze the influence of modulus of elasticity and connection stiffness separately, different numerical models were run, in which the elasticity moduli of the species were kept and the $K_{\text{shearplane}}$ values were varied. Fig. 16 shows load factor variation with the modulus of elasticity for different $K_{\text{shearplane}}$ values and the two distances between shear blocks studied. The results are referred to a maximum nodal displacement of 50.6 mm.

Figure 16. Relationship between load factor and E_{mean} for different $K_{shearplane}$ values, with 0.5 m and 1.0 m distances between shear blocks (s).

As expected, an increase in the elastic properties of the species produces a proportional increase in the overall stiffness of the arch, although the proportion depends on the stiffness of the connections. For low values of connection stiffness, the increase is very small, e.g. 22% when switching from larch to eucalyptus and 15% when switching from oak to eucalyptus in the case of $K_{shearplane}=2000$ N/mm and $s=0.5$ m. However, the increase is greater for high connection stiffnesses, e.g. 48% when switching from larch to eucalyptus and 33% when switching from oak to eucalyptus for the case of infinite connection stiffness and $s=0.5$ m. Improvements are very similar for the two distances between shear blocks studied.

Fig. 17 shows load factor variation with connection stiffness ($K_{shearplane}$) for the elasticity moduli of the studied species and the two distances between shear blocks, again at 50.6 mm of maximum nodal displacement.

Figure 17. Relationship between load factor and $K_{shearplane}$ for the different species, with 0.5 m and 1.0 m distances between shear blocks (s).

It can be seen that an increase in connection stiffness always produces an increase in arch stiffness. This increase is not proportional, as it is far greater for low values of connection stiffness and approaches zero when connection stiffness tends to infinity. Likewise, the increase in connection stiffness has a greater impact on the global stiffness of the arch when there are fewer connections and/or when the modulus of elasticity of the species is higher. For example, for a hypothetical case of increased connection stiffness from 2000 N/mm to 20000 N/mm, a 73% load increase is achieved in larch with 0.5 m between shear blocks axes and 104% when this distance is 1.0 m, while for the same cases the improvements in eucalyptus are 104% and 140%, respectively. It is interesting to note that a greater increase in arch stiffness is always achieved by doubling the number of shear blocks than it is by doubling connection stiffness. A similar conclusion was reported in [67] for an arch of 20 m span, 2 m sagitta, a composite section similar to that of the Savill gridshell and wood properties corresponding to C24 strength class.

1 It should not be forgotten that connection stiffness can be increased by increasing the diameter and/or the
2 number of connectors, as well as by increasing the density of the wood. Therefore, the above conclusions can be
3 interpreted in terms of the influence of density on arch stiffness. In practice, a change of species implies changes
4 in both the values of modulus of elasticity and density, so it becomes interesting to analyze how both aspects
5 influence the load factor simultaneously.

6 Circles in Fig. 17 indicate the load factor values in each species for the case of shear blocks connected by two 6
7 mm diameter screws per shear plane. These values obviously coincide with those shown in Fig. 13 for 50.6 mm
8 of maximum nodal displacement. As can be seen, the gain in load factor for the arch due to species change (ΔS)
9 can be understood as the sum of the gain due to the increase in the modulus of elasticity (ΔE) and the gain due to
10 the increase in density ($\Delta \rho$). The percentages of both improvements depend on the species in question and the
11 connection stiffness achieved. For the case of shear blocks connected by two 6 mm diameter screws per shear
12 plane, ΔE ranges from 8% to 37% and $\Delta \rho$ ranges from 2% to 34%. This indicates that a change in species can
13 lead to similar percentages of overall stiffness improvements due to the increases in modulus of elasticity and
14 density, at least in the case of low connection stiffness as is usual in gridshells. Although parametric analysis
15 would be necessary to extend these conclusions to other arch or gridshell geometries, this is beyond the scope of
16 this work.

17 3.3. Gridshell realisations

18 Two large structures were designed by the authors to demonstrate the potential of *Eucalyptus globulus* L. for use
19 in gridshells. Both gridshells rest on their short sides and perform longitudinally, which is an interesting
20 challenge as the elastic timber gridshells built to date are supported along their whole perimeter.

21 The first one is a barrel-vaulted full-scale laboratory prototype (Fig. 18) built with the aim of using loading tests
22 to validate a numerical model for gridshell structural analysis developed by the authors.

23 **Figure 18.** Full-scale laboratory prototype of eucalyptus gridshell.

24 The 7.5 m long prototype was composed of a grid of eucalyptus laths supported on two LVL tympanums. The
25 laths were prepared from 3 m long eucalyptus boards from which small defects were removed (visual grading)
26 but without applying any additional mechanical grading criteria. The laths were industrially connected by finger-
27 joints (at distances from 1 m to 1.5 m) using 1C-PUR adhesive according to the specifications described in
28 section 2, resulting in finger jointed solid timber of Euca 45 P1 quality. Finally, the laths were planed to a cross-
29 section of 60×25 mm².

30 The gridshell was formed by laths in three directions. Since the radius of curvature was very small in the
31 transverse direction, the corresponding laths were made of three lamellae just 8.3 mm thick, which were
32 mechanically joined by multiple small screws.

33 Two load tests were conducted on the prototype. The first was performed on a 3-layer gridshell configuration
34 (Fig 19 left), which offered a non-linear response. The second load test was carried out on the final 5-layer
35 configuration (Fig 19 middle), which showed the effectiveness of the multilayer system, providing a much more
36 rigid response, fundamentally in the elastic range. Construction details and the numerical model can be seen in
37 [68].

Figure 19. Multilayer connection systems: full-scale laboratory prototype (left and middle); Pemade gridshell (right).

A second gridshell (the Pemade gridshell) was designed as a permanent roof structure for the new wood store facility for the Timber Engineering Laboratory (PEMADE) at Santiago de Compostela University in Lugo, Spain.

The structure covers an area of $24 \times 6.5 \text{ m}^2$. A completely open frontage of 15 m in length was required to enable the storage of long wooden elements. To meet this requirement, the gridshell was supported on two *Pinus radiata* glulam arches that distance apart and resting on steel supports. This design permitted large cantilevers at the ends which protect against lateral rain (Fig. 20). Details of the design, construction process and engineering can be found in [14].

Figure 20. General view of the Pemade gridshell.

The gridshell was built using Euca GL45 $75 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$ cross-section glued laminated eucalyptus laths. The laths were made from small eucalyptus pieces of around 50 cm in average length. The use of small pieces and laminated timber made it possible to minimize the adverse effect of possible grain deviations and to improve the dimensional stability of the section against humidity changes. All the laths were manufactured according to the specifications indicated in section 2 in an industrial environment.

In this case, a 6-layer solution was designed (Fig. 19 right) in order to stiffen the structure against transverse wind loads. The shear blocking system consisted of a 12 mm diameter bolt located at each node. A lath by lath erection sequence made it possible to arrange the bolts without needing slotted holes, as was the case in Mannheim. In this way, shear transmission was through the bolts and not by friction forces. The superior performance of eucalyptus led to very high stiffness values of the laths and connections, which eliminated the need to use shear blocks in the members. This, together with the use of a translucent white post-tensioned PVC membrane as covering, gave an attractive lightweight appearance to the structure. A detail of the final view is shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21. Interior view of the Pemade gridshell.

4. Conclusions

Mechanical grading methods additional to standard visual grading criteria make it possible to considerably increase the characteristic bending strength of *Eucalyptus globulus* L. solid timber. Considering all the material, a single quality with $f_{m,k}=45$ MPa is attained. It is possible to reach up to $f_{m,k}=65$ MPa by grouping solid timber into three grades according to the modulus of elasticity.

Finger jointed solid timber laths produced from eucalyptus of different qualities leads to $f_{m,k}$ in the range of approximately 45 to 55 MPa. The best strength values are achieved using MUF adhesive.

Eucalyptus glued laminated timber laths of GL45 strength class are possible using PUR adhesive for finger-joint assembling and a single solid timber grade. The results indicate that, by using different solid timber grades, up to GL48 strength class could be reached using PUR adhesive and up to GL56 or even higher when using MUF.

Eucalyptus products perform better than those made of other species used previously in timber gridshells. Eucalyptus elastically curved laths have a smaller curvature design radius and noticeably greater stress reserve. Moreover, FEM analysis reveals higher stiffness in multilayer structural systems with semi-rigid connections.

Eucalyptus finger jointed solid timber and glued laminated timber were successfully used in two full-scale strained gridshells, highlighting the promising outlook for this species.

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Highlights

- Eucalyptus solid timber up to $f_{m,k}=65$ MPa is attained by using combined grading
- Eucalyptus finger-jointed solid timber laths of $f_{m,k}=55$ MPa are attained
- Eucalyptus glulam laths of GL56 strength class or even higher could be possible
- Eucalyptus shows higher performance than other species previously used in gridshells
- Eucalyptus products were successfully used in two full-scale strained gridshells

